

ISSUES OF GLOBALIZATION AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF HUMAN RIGHTS IN THE 21ST CENTURY.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7536120>

Abstract: In this article, first of all, the history of the development of human rights and the path taken until today, as well as the progress achieved, have been covered step by step and systematically. Information is also given on the cooperation of Uzbekistan with the UN and its specialized organization and with the European Union in the field of human rights. In addition, we have provided information about the measures taken today to strengthen human rights in our country, as well as our opinions and suggestions.

Key words: UN, European Union, humanitarian intervention, double standards, Cultural relativism, Habeas corpus.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada inson huquqlarini avvalo rivojlanish tarixi va bugungi kungacha bosib o'tilgan yo'li bundan tashqari erishilgan yutuqlarni bosqichma bosqich va tizimli yoritganmiz. O'zbekistonning BMT va uning ixtisoslashgan tashkiloti bilan va Yevropa ittifoqi bilan inson huquqlari sohasidagi hamkorligi haqida ham malumotlar berilgan. Yurtimizda inson huquqlarini mustahkamlash borasida bugungi kunda olib borilayotgan chora tadbirlar haqida malumotlar bundan tashqari fikr mulohazalarimizni berganmiz. **Kalit so'zlar:** BMT, Yevropa Ittifoqi, gumanitar intervensiya, ikki tomonlama standartlar, Madaniy relativizm, Habeas korpus.

Аннотация: В этой статье, прежде всего, шаг за шагом и систематически освещена история развития прав человека и путь, пройденный до сегодняшнего дня, а также достигнутый прогресс. Также дана информация о сотрудничестве Узбекистана с ООН и ее специализированной организацией и с Европейским Союзом в области прав человека. Кроме того, мы предоставили информацию о принимаемых сегодня мерах по укреплению прав человека в нашей стране, а также наши мнения и предложения.

Ключевые слова: ООН, Европейский союз, гуманитарная интервенция, двойные стандарты, культурный релятивизм, Habeas corpus,

Historically, it is clear to all of us that the main goal of any country is to ensure human rights, so let's first look at the development history of human rights. It

should be noted that in the early period of human development, as well as in the period of slavery, in the Middle Ages, even a couple of centuries ago, the concept of human rights in its current form, i.e. generalized, systematized or scientifically based, did not exist. In order to exist, not only the spheres of law, but also philosophy, sociology, politics, and religious lines of thinking required a historically long and gradual development. If we study Ancient Greece, which is considered to be the center of civilization, the Hellenes described in Homer's epics "Iliad" and "Odyssey" (VIII century BC) already in the period of "Homeric Greece" (the end of the 2nd millennium BC), including (truth, justice), temis (or femis-custom, customary law), time (honor, honorary right-claim), nomos (law) were used¹,,. We know that the formation of the concept of human rights spanned thousands of years, and at various times it was covered by religious, moral, or philosophical concepts. At this point, let me quote another scientist's tariff on the history of human rights. "The history of human rights is the history of the humanization of people, the progressive expansion of the legal recognition of certain people as human beings for any circle of relations,"² writes V. Nersesyans.

By the 21st century, the issue of human rights has become one of the most urgent problems of the international community. The reason why it has become an urgent problem is, firstly, that the gross and systematic violation of human rights and freedoms by the states continues, and secondly, the issue of human rights often becomes a weapon of the foreign policy of some states. As a result of this, the concepts of "double standards" and "humanitarian intervention" in human rights are emerging. The main reason for the emergence of double standards in the field of human rights is that some countries, especially (USA, some European countries) and international organizations cooperate with other countries. The fact that they are conducting different policies in the application of international norms in the field of human rights in mutual relations is the reason for the emergence of a double standard. Another problem of modern human rights is the use by some countries in their foreign policy of doctrines that are not recognized in international law on a normative basis, such as the "humanitarian intervention" theory. This problem, that is, the legitimacy of

¹ 1.Nersesyans V.S. Huquq falsafasi/ Mas'ul muharrir A.X. Saidov.-T.: Adolat, 2003.- B.177.

² 2.Nersesyans V.S. Huquq falsafasi/ Mas'ul muharrir A.X. Saidov.-T.: Adolat, 2003.- 113/bet.

using "humanitarian intervention", has been discussed at various international conferences, including the conferences of the World Association of International Law³,,. In addition, one of the most important problems of globalization today is the fight against terrorism. Its goals are the destruction of human rights, democracy and legitimacy. It is a pity that terrorism has a direct impact on the possibility of realizing human rights, especially the right to life, freedom and physical integrity, so terrorism is one of the serious threats to human rights.

Another important theoretical and practical problem in the development of human rights in the 21st century is the problem of "cultural relativism".

"Cultural relativism is a methodological instruction that rejects universal, universal values and principles, based on obvious differences specific to some local (local) cultures. Cultural relativism, applied to human rights, manifests itself in the assertion that these rights are a product of Western culture and therefore cannot be considered universal⁴,,. Relativists think as follows: they try to prove that knowledge is not real, based on the fact that it continues and changes continuously, thereby completely denying the objectivity of knowledge. Our knowledge reflects reality mostly accurately, but suddenly, after relative truths that do not fully reflect it, enriched and concretized knowledge moves towards absolute truth, which is the full and complete form of objective truth. They understand absolute truth as frozen, unchanging knowledge, and relative knowledge as only relative, and this is definitely a mistake. For example, when one theory is replaced by another in science, the old one is not completely thrown away, but its positive and correct aspects are developed. It means that the exchange of scientific theories is the result of continuous development.

By declaring its independence on August 31, 1991, the Republic of Uzbekistan recognized that it is a full-fledged member of the international relations, and entered into a full-blooded relationship, and this is stated in Article 17 of the Constitution: "The international relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a full-fledged subject of relations" he emphasized. Our country is cooperating with more than 50 different international organizations in compliance with these constitutional norms. In particular, Uzbekistan closely cooperates with the UN Human Rights Council, including its special rapporteurs and mandate holders.

³.Law and force in the New International Order.1991.Boulde.113-142 pages.

⁴.Saidov A.X.Inson huquqlari bo'yicha xalqaro xuquq.—T;Konsauditinform-Nashr,2006.179-bet.

Uzbekistan supports the initiatives of the UN in the field of human rights. In addition, Uzbekistan is cooperating with the European Union on a wide range of issues. Human rights dialogue is of particular interest in the European Union. Since 2004, regular meetings have been held at the level of the "Uzbekistan-Yale" sub-committee on justice, internal affairs, human rights and other issues based on the partnership and cooperation agreement. Within the framework of the sub-committee, intensive dialogue on human rights is conducted between Uzbekistan and Yale (European Union). The dialogue is based on the principles of democratic development, human rights and freedoms, strengthening of civil society and cooperation in this direction in Uzbekistan and other countries and non-interference in internal affairs. The European side highly appreciates the judicial reforms aimed at ensuring the independence of the judiciary in Uzbekistan, including the introduction of the institution of Habeas Corpus, ensuring the equality of the defense and the prosecution during the trial. It is clear from this that it is gratifying that in our country we are achieving results in all aspects, especially in the protection of human rights, which are recognized by other countries.

In conclusion, it should be said that the protection of human rights has become one of the most important tasks during the great reforms and renewals that are taking place in our country, which is a clear indication that democratic reforms in Uzbekistan are an irreversible process. In this regard, further expansion of active cooperation with the UN and other international organizations will certainly serve the national interests of our country.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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